

Approaches to the Synthesis of Anthracyclines and Heteroanthracyclines : Synthesis of Benzoyl-1,4-benzoquinones, their Diels-Alder Reactions and [1,5]-Rearrangement of Adducts

PAHUP SINGH*, R. T. PARDASANI, ANITA PRASHANT, C. P. POKHARNA and BHAVNA CHAUDHARY
Department of Chemistry, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur-302 004

Manuscript received 11 November 1993

Anthracyclines are of great importance in the field of medicinal chemistry. Daunorubicin, Adriamycin and Acalcinomycin A are valuable drugs for the treatment of certain human cancer¹. Carbolbicin² (I), an anthracycline derivative is a new antibiotic produced by culturing *Streptomyces coeruleorubidus*. Antibiotics DC-87-A (II) and DC-87-B are also examples of antibiotic anthracyclines³. The well documented cumulative dose dependent cardiotoxicity⁴ of these agents has motivated several efforts⁵ to synthesise new derivatives, that show decreased side-effects and/or increased anticancer activity.

A careful examination of the anthracyclines, the aglycones of anthracyclins, indicates that the benzoyl-1,4-benzoquinones may act as useful intermediates in the total synthesis of anthracyclines because these 1,4-benzoquinones may act as strong dienophiles in the Diels-Alder cycloaddition reaction with variously substituted 1,3-butadienes⁶.

The resulting adduct may undergo [1,5]-benzoyl migration to produce substituted 1,4-dihydroxynaph-

thalenes which contain an array of rings A, B and D of anthracyclines.

This property of quinones has been of great synthetic value and has been exploited in total synthesis of complex molecules including anthracyclines⁷⁻⁹. Kraus and Woo¹⁰ reported the synthesis of anthracyclines, viz. 11-deoxydaunomycinone and 4-deoxy analogues which is a good demonstration of the utility of a regioselective Diels-Alder cycloaddition. Gupta *et al.*¹¹ also reported a regioselective synthesis of 4-demethoxydaunomycinone.

Thus a wide variety of benzoyl-1,4-benzoquinones have been synthesised in our laboratory over the last decade which are listed in Table 1. These quinones have been subjected to the Diels-Alder reaction with various 1,3-dienes, viz. *trans*-piperylene, isoprene, 2,3-dimethyl-1,3-butadiene, 1-methoxy-1,3-butadiene, Danishefsky's

diene etc. to afford adducts (7), which are summarised in Table 2. The adduct underwent smooth [1,5]-benzoyl migration in pyridine at room temperature to give benzoyl-substituted-1,4-dihydroxynaphthalenes (8) (Table 3).

Table-1(contd.)

Sl. no.	Compd.	M p °C	Yield %	Ref. no.
1.	2-(4'-Fluorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	95-96	72	12
2.	2-(3'-Fluorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	81	76	12
3.	2-(3'-Trifluoromethylbenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	79	80	12
4.	2-(4'-Fluoro-2'-methylbenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	79	93	12
5.	2-(4'-Trifluoromethylbenzoyl)-5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone	120	89	12
6.	2-(4'-Fluorobenzoyl)-5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone	96	84	12
7.	2-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	158	59	13
8.	2-(2',4'-Dichlorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	148	72	13
9.	6-Bromo-2-(2'-chlorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	—	78	13
10.	6-Bromo-2-(4'-chlorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	123	83	13
11.	2-(2'-Chlorobenzoyl)-6-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone	102	96	13
12.	6-Bromo-2-(3'-chlorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	114	60	14
13.	6-Bromo-2-(2',4'-dichlorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	114	67	14
14.	2-(2',4'-Dichlorobenzoyl)-6-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone	115	97	13
15.	2-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-6-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone	120	80	13
16.	2-(3'-Methyl-4'-nitrobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	120	86	12
17.	2-(2'-Fluorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	73	66	12
18.	2-(2'-Fluorobenzoyl)-5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone	107	80	12
19.	2-(3'-Fluorobenzoyl)-5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone	74	90	12
20.	2-(3'-Fluorobenzoyl)-5-fluoro-1,4-benzoquinone	94	89	12
21.	2-(3'-Chloro-4'-fluorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	101	80	15
22.	2-(2'-Chloro-4'-fluorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	127	63	15
23.	5-Amino-2-(4'-fluorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	96	79	15

24.	5-Amino-2-(2'-fluorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	104	79	15
25.	5-Amino-2-(4'-trifluoromethylbenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	100	74	15
26.	2-(2'-Fluorobenzoyl)-5-fluoro-1,4-benzoquinone	119	80	16
27.	2-(2'-Chlorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	142	81	16
28.	2-(3'-Chlorobenzoyl)-1,4-benzoquinone	156	56	16
29.	2-(4'-Fluorobenzoyl)-5-fluoro-1,4-benzoquinone	96	70	16
30.	2-(2'-Fluorobenzoyl)-5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone	170	75	16
31.	2-(2'-Chloro-4'-fluorobenzoyl)-5-methyl-1,4-benzoquinone	127	67	16
32.	2-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-6-(4'-chlorobenzamido)-1,4-benzoquinone	129	72	16

TABLE 2—ADDUCTS OF BENZOYL-1,4-BENZOQUINONES (7)

Compd. no	Compd.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Ref. no.
7a	3-Bromo-4a-(2'-chlorobenzoyl)-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-7-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone	94	87	19
b	3-Bromo-4a-(3'-chlorobenzoyl)-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-7-methyl-1,4-naphthoquinone	109	74	19
c	4a-(2'-Chlorobenzoyl)-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-3,7-dimethyl-1,4-naphthoquinone	107	94	19
d	4a-(2'-Chlorobenzoyl)-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-3,5-dimethyl-1,4-naphthoquinone	112	92	19
e	4a-(2',4'-Dichlorobenzoyl)-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-2,7-dimethyl-1,4-naphthoquinone	100	84	19
f	4a-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-2,6,7-trimethyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinone	105	80	19
g	4a-(3'-Methyl-4'-nitrobenzoyl)-5-methyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinone	90	80	19
h	4a-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-5-methyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinone	118	84	19
i	4a-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-6,7-dimethyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinone	108	79	19
j	4a-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-7-methyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinone	98	90	19
k	4a-(2',4'-Dichlorobenzoyl)-5-methyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinone	104	88	19

Table-2 (contd)

l	4a-(2',4'-Dichlorobenzoyl)-7-methyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinone	109	78	19
m	4a-(4'-Fluorobenzoyl)-5-methyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinone	89	80	10
n	4a-(3'-Trifluoromethylbenzoyl)-5-methyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinone	124	65	20
o	4a-(4'-Fluorobenzoyl)-2,5-dimethyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinone	102	78	20

TABLE 3-1,5-REARRANGEMENT OF ADDUCTS SYNTHESIS OF 1,4-DIHYDROXYNAPHTHALENES (8)

Compd no	Compd	M p °C	Yield %	Ref no
8a	3-Bromo-2-(2'-chlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-6-methyl naphthalene	-	92	19
b	3-Bromo-2-(4'-chlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-6-methyl naphthalene	-	87	19
c	2-(2'-Chlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-3,6-dimethylnaphthalene	-	94	19
d	2-(2'-Chlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-3,8-dimethylnaphthalene	-	96	19
e	2-(2',4'-Dichlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-3,6-dimethylnaphthalene	-	78	19
f	2-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-3,6,7-trimethylnaphthalene	-	74	19
g	2-(3'-Methyl-4'-nitrobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-8-methylnaphthalene	104	83	19
h	2-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-8-methylnaphthalene	128	98	19
i	2-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-6,7-dimethylnaphthalene	142	78	19
j	2-(4'-Chlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-6-methylnaphthalene	105	92	19
k	2-(2',4'-Dichlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-8-methylnaphthalene	-	86	19
l	2-(2',4'-Dichlorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-6-methylnaphthalene	-	84	19
m	2-(4'-Fluorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-8-methylnaphthalene	-	90	20
n	2-(3'-Trifluoromethyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-8-methylnaphthalene	-	76	20
o	2-(4'-Fluorobenzoyl)-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxy-3,8-dimethylnaphthalene	-	89	20

Results and Discussion

All the benzoyl-1,4-benzoquinones were syn-

thesised by a three-step route. Substituted-1,4-dimethoxybenzenes (**2**) on condensation with an excess of an appropriate benzoic acid (**1**) in the presence of polyphosphoric acid (PPA) formed the ketones (**3**) which on demethylation with boron tribromide (BBr₃) in dry dichloromethane at 0° gave yellow crystalline hydroquinones (**4**). The hydroquinones (**4**) were oxidised to the corresponding quinones (**5**) using 6–8 folds excess of silver oxide¹⁷ in dry benzene at 35° as orange-red crystalline products (Scheme 1). All these compounds were characterised on the basis of their ir, ¹H and ¹³C nmr spectral data.

Scheme 1

In case of some sensitive acids, the PPA condensation method failed and in such cases, the ketones were alternatively prepared by the acid chloride method. Such sensitive acids were converted into the respective acid chloride on Freidel-Craft arylation with dimethoxybenzene in the presence of anhydrous AlCl₃ gave the desired ketones (Scheme 2).

Scheme 2

In the same manner, heteroanthracynone intermediates were synthesised. 1,4-Dimethoxythioxanthen-9-one was prepared by condensation of 2,2'-dithiosalicylic acid and 1,4-dimethoxybenzene

which was demethylated with boron tribromide to give the corresponding hydroquinone. *In situ* oxidation with silver oxide followed by addition to various dienes gave 6a,7,10,10a-tetrahydrobenzothioxanthen-6,11,12-triones (Scheme 3).

Scheme 3

The Diels-Alder reactions of the newly synthesised benzoyl-1,4-benzoquinones (5) were conducted with various dienes (6) and the [1,5]-rearrangements of the resulting adducts (7) afforded 1,4-dihydroxynaphthalenes (8) (Scheme 4) which contain basic skeleton (rings A, B and D) of anthracyclinones. The interesting feature of 1,5-rearrangement is that the benzoyl shifts in dry pyridine occur at 35° instead of higher temperature as reported by other workers¹⁸.

All the products were properly characterised on the basis of their spectral data. Thus the dimethoxyketones showed C=O stretch at 1680–1630 cm⁻¹ in their ir spectra whereas the C–O–C stretching vibration appeared at 1260–1020 cm⁻¹. ¹H nmr spectra showed two sharp singlets around δ 3.50 and 3.95 for methoxy protons and the aromatic protons appeared at δ 7.1–8.0.

	R ¹	R ²	R ³	R ⁴	R ⁵	R ⁶	R ⁷
7, 8a,	Cl	H	H	Br	H	H	CH ₃
b,	H	H	Cl	Br	H	H	CH ₃
c,	Cl	H	H	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃
d,	Cl	H	H	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	H
e,	Cl	H	Cl	CH ₃	H	H	CH ₃
f,	H	H	Cl	CH ₃	H	CH ₃	CH ₃
g,	H	CH ₃	NO ₂	H	CH ₃	H	H
h,	H	H	Cl	H	CH ₃	H	H
i,	H	H	Cl	H	H	CH ₃	CH ₃
j,	H	H	Cl	H	H	H	CH ₃
k,	Cl	H	Cl	H	CH ₃	H	H
l,	Cl	H	Cl	H	H	H	CH ₃
m,	H	H	F	H	CH ₃	H	H
n,	H	CF ₃	H	H	CH ₃	H	H
o,	H	H	F	CH ₃	CH ₃	H	H

Scheme 4

Ir spectra of the hydroquinones exhibited broad peak in the region 3500–3260 cm⁻¹ confirming the presence of free and hydrogen bonded OH. Besides, the carbonyl stretching vibrations appeared at its usual frequency at 1680–1610 cm⁻¹ and disappearance of both methoxy singlets in the ¹H nmr spectra as well as appearance of hydroxy protons at δ 4.5–12.0 further confirmed the demethylation. Aromatic protons were seen in the range δ 7.0–7.7.

The absence of broad peaks in the ir spectra of the benzoyl-1,4-benzoquinones in the region 3500–3260 cm⁻¹ showed the disappearance of hydroxyl groups. The quinonoid carbonyl stretching bands appeared at 1690–1630 cm⁻¹. In the

pmr spectra of these quinones, hydroxy signals in the range δ 4.5–12.0 were absent whereas the quinonoid protons appeared at δ 6.6–6.9 either as multiplet or as broad singlet with some fine structure, and the aromatic protons appeared in the range δ 7.1–8.0. In addition, all the compounds showed satisfactory elemental analyses.

Mass spectra of some of the quinones were recorded and it displayed respective molecular ion peaks.

Experimental

Melting points were determined on electrothermal apparatus in open glass capillaries and are uncorrected. Ir spectra were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 557 grating spectrophotometer, ^1H and ^{13}C nmr spectra (CDCl_3 or CCl_4) on a Jeol FX 90Q FT NMR spectrometer (90 MHz) using TMS as an internal standard and mass spectra were recorded on a Varian-Mat 711 instrument. Preparative tlc was performed on Kieselgel PF₂₅₄, 60F₂₅₄ precoated silica gel plates (Merck). The purity of the compounds was checked on tlc plates in various solvent systems.

2,5-Dimethoxybenzophenones (3) : A mixture of an appropriate benzoic acid (15 mmol) substituted/unsubstituted dimethoxybenzene (15 mmol) and polyphosphoric acid (90 ml) was heated at 60–70° with vigorous stirring in an oil-bath for 6–7 h. The resulting red solution was slowly poured into warm water (300 ml) and allowed to cool. It was then extracted with solvent ether, washed with sodium bicarbonate solution and distilled water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate for 2–3 h. Removal of the solvent afforded coloured products which were crystallised from petroleum-ether (b.p. 60–80°), (40–83%).

2,5-Dihydroxybenzophenones (4) : The ketones (3) were dissolved in dry dichloromethane (15 ml) and to it was added a solution of boron tribromide (15–40 mmol) in dichloromethane at 0°. The resulting red solution was stirred for

15–17 h and then decomposed with water (30 ml). After separating aqueous layer, the organic layer was washed with water and dried over anhydrous magnesium sulphate. It was filtered and concentrated under reduced pressure to yield yellow shining crystals of hydroquinones (4; 70–95%).

Benzoyl-1,4-benzoquinones (5) : A mixture of the hydroquinones (4; 0.5–3 mmol), silver oxide (1.5–18 mmol) and anhydrous sodium sulphate (1–3 g) in dry C_6H_6 (15–40 ml) was stirred at room temperature with intermittent shaking for 6 h. The resulting solution was filtered through celite and evaporated to dryness to furnish orange-red solids which were crystallised from petroleum ether- CHCl_3 , (59–79%).

4a-Benzoyl-4a,5,8,8a-tetrahydro-1,4-naphthoquinones (7) (adducts) : The benzoyl-1,4-benzoquinones (5) were dissolved in dry benzene and to it was added excess of suitably substituted dienes (6) at room temperature. The resulting solution was left overnight at room temperature. Evaporation of the solvent then afforded coloured solids which were crystallised from cyclohexane/petroleum ether to yield the adducts.

2-Benzoyl-5,8-dihydro-1,4-dihydroxynaphthalenes (8) : The adducts (7) were dissolved in dry pyridine and kept at room temperature until rearrangement was complete (36–48 h). The solvent was then removed under reduced pressure and exchanged with methanol to furnish brown-red solid or oil as products.

References

1. F. ARCAMONE, *Top. Antibiot Chem.*, 1978, 102; "Anthracyclines : Current Status and New Developments", eds S. T. CROOKE and S. D. REICH, Academic, New York, 1980; "Anticancer Agents Based on Natural Product Models", eds J. M. CASSADY and J. D. DOURES, Academic, New York, 1980; H. S. EL KHADEM, "Anthracycline Antibiotics", Academic, New York, 1982; A. V. R. RAO, *Proc. Indian Acad. Sci. (Chem. Sci.)*, 1984, 93, 1059; M. J. BROADHURST, C. H. HASALL and G. J. THOMAS, *Chem. Ind.*, 1985, 106.
2. Sanraku Ocean Co. Ltd., Jap. Pat. JP 6 001 300/1985.
3. Sanraku Ocean Co. Ltd., Jap. Pat. JP 6 001 152/1985.

4. L. LENAZ and J. A. MAGE, *J. Am. Cancer Treat. Rep.*, 1976, **3**, 111; D. D. VONHOFF, M. LAYARD, M. ROSENCWEIZ and F. M. MUGGIA, *J. Am. Cancer Treat. Rep.*, 1977, **61**, 1411.
5. C. J. SIH, D. MASSUDA, P. COREY, R. D. GLEIM and F. SUZUKI, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1979, 1285; M. CHANDLER and R. J. STOODLEY, *J. Chem. Soc., Chem. Commun.*, 1978, 997; A. V. R. RAO, V. H. DESHPANDE and N. L. REDDY, *Tetrahedron Lett.*, 1980, **21**, 2661; P. N. CONALONE and G. PIZZOLATO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1980, **55**, 5520.
6. A. S. ONISCHENKO, "Diene Synthesis", Program of Scientific Translations Dieniel Davy, New York, 1964.
7. Y. KISHI, M. ARATANI, T. FUKUYAMA, N. NAKATSUVO, T. GOTO, S. INOUL, H. TANINI, S. SUGURRA and H. KAKOI, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **94**, 9217.
8. J. P. GESSON, J. C. JACQUSEY and B. RENOUX, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, **40**, 4743.
9. J. M. MC NAMARA and Y. KISHI, *Tetrahedron*, 1984, **40**, 4685.
10. A. G. KRAUS and H. S. WOO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1987, **52**, 4841.
11. R. C. GUPTA, D. C. JACKSON, R. J. STOODLEY and D. J. WILLIAMS, *J. Chem., Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1985, 525.
12. K. C. JOSHI, R. T. PARDASANI and Y. S. MURTADHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect., B*, 1992, **31**, 267.
13. P. SINGH, R. T. PARDASANI, A. PRASHANT, C. P. POKHARNA and B. CHAUDHARY, *Pharmazie*, 1993, **48**, 699.
14. C. P. POKHARNA, B. CHAUDHARY, R. T. PARDASANI and P. SINGH, *Indian J. Pharm. Sci.*, 1993, communicated.
15. Y. S. MURTADHA, Thesis, unpublished work, 1987.
16. A. PRASHANT, Thesis, unphlished work, 1992.
17. H. ULRICH and D. RAO, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1977, **42**, 3444
18. D. S. FIELD, D. W. JONES and G. KHEEN, *J. Chem Soc., Perkin Trans. 1*, 1978, 1050.
19. B. CHAUDHARY, C. P. POKHARNA, A. PRASHANT, R. T. PARDASANI and P. SINGH, *Pharmazie*, 1993, **48**, 943.
20. K. C. JOSHI, R. T. PARDASANI, A. PRASHANT and Y. S. MURTADHA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. B*, 1993, **32**, 681.